

Cultural Issues in Coalition Planning

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Abstract—*This paper outlines the cultural issues that manifest in the planning and decision-making phases of coalition operations. It then summarizes the current status of emerging tools for identifying cultural differences, with respect to supporting coalition planning activities. The emphasis is on cultural variations in cognition, language, distributed social interaction, as well as their interrelationships. In particular, the paper describes Cultural Network Analysis for extracting and representing culturally shared, complex mental representations that drive decisions; tools for the assessment of commander’s intent across coalition boundaries; and methods for investigating social interactions and language in multicultural distributed collaboration settings.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Coalition operations have emerged as a key feature of military operations in the post-Cold War era. Indeed, it is now the standard mode across the spectrum of military interventions, with virtually all U.S. and U.K. operations over the last two decades having been conducted as part of a coalition [1]. A coalition typically consists of a collection of distinct state militaries¹, as well as non-military organizations such as departments of state, multinational agencies (e.g., UN), non-governmental groups (NGOs, media, relatives), and sometimes agents of the host nation. Each of these groups differ in size, composition in terms of age and gender, activities performed on the ground and ways of performing them, reasons for participation, and success criteria of the operation. Furthermore, they bring their own cultural backgrounds that influence their decision-making and collaborative styles,

¹ For example, “the military presence established in Bosnia-Herzegovina following the end of their civil war included participants from over 38 nations” [2].

natural and doctrinal languages, technological capabilities, and core competencies.

Cultural differences can and do lead to tensions between coalition partners. For instance, Winslow’s [3] study of UN peace operations identified the seven areas of tensions between military and other groups in theater (including other national militaries): organizational composition, different tasks and ways of accomplishing them, differing time frames, different definitions of success, different abilities to exert influence, control of information, and control of resources. These cultural issues come into play at all stages of operations: planning, giving and taking orders, executing orders and reporting. The focus of the current paper, however, is on the cultural issues that arise in coalition planning and decision making.

2. CULTURAL ISSUES IN PLANNING

Culture has come to the fore as a critical area for developing current and future capabilities. For example, Petraeus reported that recent experiences in Afghanistan and Iraq show that “cultural awareness is a force multiplier.” That is, knowledge of the cultural “terrain” can be as important as, and sometimes even more important than, knowledge of the geographic terrain [4]. Scales cast the situation even more starkly: “it is more important to understand motivation, intent, method, and culture than to have a few more meters of precision, knots of speed, or bits of bandwidth” [5].

Much of this discussion about cultural issues rightfully emphasizes the cultures of the adversary and populace from the host nation. For example, Yates’ analysis of the historical record points out a need to look at not only what resources the military can bring to bear to solve anticipated problems, but how the local population and its leaders will respond to

actions the military undertakes to address those problems [6].

However, cultural differences exist even among the closest of coalition partners, such as between the U.S. and U.K. militaries. Understanding culture within the core of a coalition amounts to developing a deep understanding of “ourselves” rather than our host, and in many cases raises a distinct set of cultural issues that matter in that particular context. For example, eating behaviors may have an impact on relationships between members of the military and host nation, but have little bearing on the coalition team putting together a campaign plan.

The increased attention to culture has not arisen in a vacuum, but rather in response to a shift in the requirements for current and envisioned future warfare. Chiarelli and Michaelis described requirements for full-spectrum operations, including the simultaneous pursuit of the development of economic pluralism, promoting governance, restoration and improvement of essential services, and training and employing host nation security forces, all in addition to combat operations and with a primary emphasis on “winning the peace” [7]. Pierce and Dixon have identified these new challenges as constituting a special case of a “wicked problem” [8]. Wicked problems have no known solutions or single right answers, but instead include myriad evolving issues and constraints that demand solutions that satisfy for the relevant stakeholders. In such cases, multiple stakeholders with distinct agendas must come together to discuss the elements of the ill-defined and changing problem space in order to develop generally acceptable and adaptable plans. Hence, coalition planning and decision making emerges as the center of gravity for successfully handling wicked problems. The significance is that these core processes must be adapted to be truly integrative and inclusive of the represented coalition members in a way that capitalizes on the benefits of their cultural diversity. Wicked problems cannot be solved by one major player driving the planning and decision-making processes.

A first step in realizing the required level of inclusiveness is to model the diversity of coalition planning and decision-making processes in terms of their meaning, expectations, rules, and norms. In order to support a team of coalition planners who are planning a campaign involving full spectrum operations, we need to first understand the differences between the partners’ concepts of plans, plan quality, and the tools and processes believed to yield high-quality plans. These concepts can differ in potentially significant ways, including: 1) whether goals are seen as fundamentally clear or vague in specification; 2) whether the ideal is a highly detailed plan such that execution cannot begin until all ambiguities are removed, or the ideal is a general concept to which details will be added once the action starts; 3) whether plan revisions are viewed as necessary for adaptability or indicators of poor planning; 4) what the basic functions of a plan are considered to be; 5) how the plans are structured and the way they are communicated to sub-units. This initial list of potential differences in plans and planning needs to be expanded upon and validated. It also needs to be more deeply understood in terms of the relevant cultural and contextual pressures.

Though being “culturally aware” is now seen to be essential, military have always been cognizant of differences between service arms (air, land, and sea) and possible confusions are minimized through use of Liaison Officers and joint training. This strategy is also successfully employed with close coalition partners who participate in multinational training exercises and exchange Liaison Officers to mitigate the problem of language and potential cultural misunderstandings. Unfortunately, this strategy works only in well-defined conflict scenarios in which friends and enemies are constant, and there is ample time to get to know the coalition partners. Conflicts in the past decade have been marked by asymmetric opponents and very fluid coalitions put together in short time frames. As a consequence, the benefits of Liaison Officers and multinational training exercises cannot be relied upon for “new” coalition partners.

3. RESEARCH ON CULTURAL ANALYSIS

Current methods for understanding cultural differences include ethnographic methods that focus on qualitative analysis of a single cultural group, and psychological methods that attempt to capture cultural differences in a few generic dimensions, such as individualism/collectivism. Such methods are limited in their ability to capture and represent cultural commonalities and disconnects with the precision needed to enable the design of complex cognitive systems, such as coalition command. Hence, there is a need for rigorous methods to capture, analyze, represent, and compare the cognitive, linguistic, and social dynamics of cultures.

Recently, several efforts have gotten underway to research, develop, and evaluate new approaches to enhance multicultural collaboration in coalitions. For example, Pierce and Dixon describe several technologies under development by the U.S. Army Research Laboratory [8]. More recently, the International Technology Alliance (ITA) between the U.K. Ministry of Defense and the U.S. Army Research Laboratory has devoted one of its twelve interdisciplinary projects to culture. Specifically, the overall objective of the "Cultural Analysis" project in the ITA is to explore the development of methods to advance the state of the art of cultural analysis. A second objective is to employ these methods to analyze key cultural issues in coalition operations, especially planning, decision making, and negotiation. The challenge is to develop methods that can detect and represent the more subtle differences that do exist between culturally similar national partners engaging in collaborative planning and decision making, than could be accounted for using existing approaches.

Cultural Network Analysis

Cultural Network Analysis (CNA) refers to a collection of methodologies for building cultural models [9]. Cultural Network Analysis includes methods to first elicit and analyze the mental models of a sample of individuals within the population, and second measure the degree to which elements of the mental models are

shared across individuals. Lastly, CNA provides a framework for representing the culture. A fully developed, analytical cultural model represents the statistical distribution of mental models for a particular cultural group and domain. Formal representation makes it possible to use cultural models in a variety of applied contexts. Cultural Network Analysis can be used to build cultural models of collaborative planning and decision making, in addition to other macrocognitive functions.

Cultural Network Analysis is an outgrowth of the cultural epidemiology theoretical view of culture as comprising distributions of networks of causally-interconnected ideas within populations (i.e. mental models). Cultural Network Analysis builds on a synthesis of conceptually related methods for knowledge elicitation, analysis, and representation that stem from the diverse fields of naturalistic decision making, cognitive anthropology, cognitive psychology, and decision analysis. Prior to the development of CNA, none of these fields alone has offered a comprehensive, end-to-end approach for cultural modeling.

Tools for the Assessment of Command Intent

A second methodology being proposed is a tool for improving the assessment of Commander's Intent in coalition settings [10]. The process of a subordinate commander receiving and interpreting orders from a higher level in the command structure, and developing and issuing his own orders from them, is well documented for both U.S. and U.K. forces, but assessment of the process, especially when U.S.-U.K. coalition operations are considered, will be greatly assisted by a well-defined method, and measurement tool based upon it. Development of the tool for improving the assessment of Commander's Intent will be based on measuring the effectiveness of commanders and sub-commanders in interpreting and developing orders. Applied to coalition force command structures, it will allow assessment of the influence of command language and culture on U.S.-U.K. coalition operational effectiveness. It will also provide the first step in the development of quantitative measures related to actual transmission of orders.

Measures for Analysis of Distributed Social Interactions

The third emphasis is on communication patterns. There are at least two different communication means of interest: face-to-face and facilitated by electronic communications. The primary concern in the development of the current measures is with mediated communications. Specifically, a variety of communication applications will be instrumented and used to analyze and measure the cross-cultural variability of communications at several levels, including: social network analysis, communication pattern analysis, communication behavior analysis, conversation and discourse analysis, and communication content analysis. A special emphasis area within the discourse analysis is to improve on the understanding of pragmatics. Parallel work in computational language analysis is focusing on meaning using techniques such as Latent Semantic Analysis [8]. In the ITA effort, the emphasis is at the level of communicating intent through what is said, as well as how it is said [11]. This focus will provide the type of “conversation analysis” required to address the needs of US-UK coalition C2 requirements.

4. SUMMARY

U.S.-U.K. coalition and joint operations often face operationally and environmentally complex and dynamic scenarios, which require highly synchronized coordination and adaptive capability. New methodologies for cultural analysis that are required to meet these challenges are currently under development under the International Technology Alliance.

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